

A Novel Heterocyclic System from Dicoumarols

PASUPATI SENGUPTA*, (MISS) MANJU SEN, SANJIB KUMAR DAS and PRADIP KARURI

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

and

ERNEST WENKERT and T. D. J. HALLS

Department of Chemistry, University of California, San Diego, La Jolla, California 92093, U.S.A.

Treatment of compounds 1c, 1e and 1g with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine yielded novel zwitterionic heterocyclic systems 3a, 3b and 3c respectively. A mechanistic path has been suggested for this conversion. To substantiate the mechanism this model system 4 has been converted to similar zwitterionic system 5.

In a previous communication¹ we reported the isolation of gerberinol from *Gerbera lanuginosa* Benth. and established its structure as 5,5'-dimethyldicoumarol (1a). We also reported that on treatment with acetic anhydride and pyridine, gerberinol (1a) did not yield the diacetate (1b), instead it gave the anhydro compound (2a). However under identical conditions dicoumarol (1c), 6,6'-dimethyldicoumarol (1e) and 8,8'-dimethyldicoumarol (1g) yielded the corresponding diacetates 1d, 1f and 1i respectively.

We wanted to examine if dicoumarol (1c) could also be converted into the anhydro compound (2b) on simple treatment with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine. But instead of the desired anhydro compound (2b) we isolated a complex compound C₂₂H₁₈NO₄, m.p. above 345° (M⁺ 379) containing nitrogen. Its spectra showed bands at 1750 (lactone carbonyl) but no band at 3000–3500 cm⁻¹, indicating the absence of OH group. The nmr spectra showed thirteen aromatic protons in the region from δ 6.82–8.50.

Dicoumarol has no nitrogen, thus it may be assumed that pyridine, the only nitrogen containing compound in the reaction medium, has been incorporated. In order to explain the analytical and spectral data and on mechanistic grounds we suggest structure 3a for this nitrogenous compound.

When 6,6'-dimethyldicoumarol (1e)¹ was similarly treated with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine, we isolated the corresponding nitrogenous compound (3b) C₂₆H₁₇NO₄, m.p. 261–63° (M⁺ 407). The nmr spectra showed two aromatic methyl groups at δ 2.22 (6H, s) and eleven aromatic protons in the region δ 6.82–8.57.

8,8'-Dimethyldicoumarol (1g)¹ on similar treatment with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine yielded the nitrogenous compound (3c), C₂₆H₁₇NO₄, m.p. 252–53° (M⁺ 407). Two singlets (3H each) at δ 2.25 and 2.35 were due to the two aromatic methyl groups. Signals for eleven aromatic protons appeared in the region δ 7–8.80.

- 1a, R², R³ = H, R¹ = Me
 b, R² = R³ = H, R¹ = Me, R = Ac
 c, R = R¹ = R² = R³ = H
 d, R¹ = R² = R³ = H, R = Ac
 e, R = R¹ = R³ = H, R² = Me
 f, R¹ = R³ = H, R² = Me, R = Ac
 g, R = R¹ = R² = H, R³ = Me
 i, R¹ = R² = H, R³ = Me, R = Ac

- 2a, R = Me
 b, R = H

A plausible mechanism for the formation of the novel heterocyclic system (3) is outlined in Scheme 1. To get more insight in the mechanistic path we carried the reaction of phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine on a model compound (4)². In this case also we obtained nitrogenous product C₁₇H₁₁NO₄, m.p. 224–26° (M⁺ 293) to which we attributed structure 5. The mechanism for the formation of 5 from 4 is shown in Scheme 2.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes :

Preparation of 3a. Phosphorus oxychloride pyridine treatment of dicoumarol (1c): POCl₃ (10 ml) was added slowly to a solution of dicoumarol (1c) in pyridine (60 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature, then boiled for 5 min, cooled and poured slowly with stirring

Scheme 1

into crushed ice. A black amorphous solid that appeared was filtered, washed and dried. The solid was purified by column chromatography followed by crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform-acetone to give yellow crystals (3a; 0.25 g), m.p. above 345° (Found: C, 75.79; H, 3.55; N, 3.77. $C_{22}H_{18}NO_4$ requires: C, 75.98; H, 3.55; N, 3.65%); m/e 379 (M^+ , 95.8%), 362 (27.46), 351 (20.44), 335 (100), 306 (16.24), 294 (20.26) and 278 (42.06).

Preparation of 3b. Phosphorus oxychloride-pyridine treatment of 6,6'-dimethyl dicoumarol (1e): 6,6'-Dimethyldicoumarol (1e) when treated with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine using the above method gave 3b, m.p. 261–63° (Found: C, 77.02; H, 4.28; N, 3.79. $C_{22}H_{18}NO_4$ requires: C, 76.65; H, 4.21; N, 3.41%); m/e 407 (M^+ , 83.38%), 390 (26.76), 379 (12.01) and 363 (100).

Preparation of 3c. Reaction of 8,8'-dimethyldicoumarol (1g) with phosphorus oxychloride-pyridine: 8,8'-Dimethyl dicoumarol (1g)¹ prepared by the

usual method on treatment with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine using the above method afforded compound 3c, m.p. 252–53° (Found: C, 75.64; H, 4.34; N, 3.39. $C_{22}H_{18}NO_4$ requires: C, 75.65; H, 4.2; N, 3.44%); m/e 407 (M^+ , 100%), 390 (5.49), 379 (15.95) and 363 (53.13).

Preparation of methyl ester of 4-hydroxycoumarin-3-acetic acid (4): A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin-3-acetic acid (0.5 g), prepared by the usual method², dry MeOH (5 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.25 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The mixture was kept at room temperature overnight and then poured into ice-cooled water when a solid mass settled at the bottom. It was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from chloroform-light petroleum to give white crystals of methyl ester (4; 0.25 g), m.p. 179–80° (Found: C, 61.41; H, 4.28. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ calcd. for: C, 61.54; H, 4.30%); m/e 234 (M^+ , 48.52%), 202 (100), 175 (54.80), 174 (20.5%), 121 (49.56) and 120 (19.31).

Scheme 2

Preparation of 5. Phosphorus oxychloride – pyridine treatment of methyl ester of 4-hydroxycoumarin-3-acetic acid (4) : Phosphorus oxychloride (2 ml)

was slowly added to a solution of 4 (0.2 g) in pyridine (12 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand overnight, then boiled for 5 min, cooled and poured slowly with stirring into crushed ice when red solid appeared at the bottom. It was filtered, washed with water, dilute HCl and finally with water. The solid upon chromatographic separation followed by crystallisation from chloroform – light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) furnished reddish crystals (5; 0.074 g), m.p. 224–26° (Found : C, 69.49; H, 3.52; N, 4.71. $C_{17}H_{11}NO_4$ calcd. for : C, 69.52; H, 3.78; N, 4.78%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 730–1 740 (lactone group) and 1 570–1 620 (aromatic nucleus); δ ($CDCl_3$) 4.00 (3H, s) and 6.92–8.80 (8H, m); m/e 293 (M^+ , 92.7%), 262 (100), 235 (37.03) and 206 (22.22).

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References

1. P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, P. KARURI, E. WENKERT and T. D. J. HALLS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 916.
2. A. MULLER and J. SCHNEIDER, *Monatsch. Chem.*, 1949, **80**, 282